

ACVR1 Crystals at the Diamond Light Source – Beamline I04.

Crystals of ACVR1 bound to one of three different compounds (M4K2192, 2163 or 2143) were sent to the Diamond Light Source on the 4th of May 2019 to beamline I04.

Details for beamline I04 can be found here: <https://www.diamond.ac.uk/Instruments/Mx/I04>

Crystals were centred in the beamline using the autocentering algorithms which did not satisfactorily align the crystal in the beam in all cases. Autocentering was used as standard for this trip due to the combination of pressure on beam time requiring swift crystal analysis and the overnight timing of the trip meaning I could not attend to the crystals personally.

The following is a summary of the crystals:

Mounted Crystal ID (Mounted Crystal)	Crystal to be Mounted (Mounted Crystal)	Mounted Crystal Comments (Mounted Crystal)	Synchrotron comments
ACVR1A-x518	CI074750-C09c	M4K2192	possible rotation out of beam. Some diffraction
ACVR1A-x519	CI074750-C09c	M4K2192	missed beam
ACVR1A-x520	CI074750-C09c	M4K2192	missed beam
ACVR1A-x521	CI074750-C09a	M4K2192	rotated out of beam diffraction seen
ACVR1A-x522	CI074865-E09c	M4K2163	missed beam
ACVR1A-x523	CI074865-E09c	M4K2163	missed beam
ACVR1A-x524	CI074861-E09c	M4K2143	missed beam
ACVR1A-x525	CI074863-F04c	M4K2143	missed beam
ACVR1A-x526	CI074863-F07a	M4K2143	in beam no diffraction
ACVR1A-x527	CI074865-D 11a	M4K2163	rotated out of beam diffraction seen
ACVR1A-x528	CI074752-D04c	M4K2143	in beam no diffraction
ACVR1A-x529	CI074752-C09c	M4K2143	missed beam
ACVR1A-x530	CI074752-C09d	M4K2143	rotated out of beam diffraction seen
ACVR1A-x531	CI074751-A05d	M4K2192	missed beam
ACVR1A-x532	CI074751-A05d	M4K2192	missed beam
ACVR1A-x533	CI074751-E04d	M4K2192	missed beam
ACVR1A-x534	CI074751-E04c	M4K2192	poor diffraction, possible rotation out of beam
ACVR1A-x535	CI074751-E12a	M4K2192	unsure - possibly missed crystal or possibly just poor diffraction
ACVR1A-x536	CI074861-E10a	M4K2143	missed beam
ACVR1A-x537	CI074861-E10a	M4K2143	missed beam
ACVR1A-x538	CI074863-F05a	M4K2143	in beam no diffraction

Green highlighted rows showed some diffraction but also look like they rotated out of the beam.

Red rows were aligned correctly but showed no diffraction.

All other rows appeared to have missed the beam completely.

All crystals were shot under a nitrogen stream so should be ok to reshoot at the next diamond trip on beamline I04-1 using manual crystal alignment.

Fig. 1 – Beam aligned at very edge of loop showing cyclic diffraction suggesting the crystal was moving in and out of the beam rather than degrading in the beam.

Fig. 2 Complete misalignment of beam shows it shooting through the stem of the loop rather than the crystal in the loop.

Crystals will be reflagged and sent on the next trip on the 17th of May on beamline I04-1.